

Research Article

Kelantan Cultural Heritage through Coffee Painting as a Medium

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Abstract: Kelantan's cultural heritage, deeply rooted in its traditions and artistic expressions, is facing challenges from modern influences and globalization, which threaten the preservation of its unique identity. This paper examines the innovative use of coffee painting as a medium to safeguard and promote Kelantan's cultural heritage. The study identifies the problem of diminishing traditional art forms and explores coffee painting as a creative solution to engage both local communities and a global audience. By using coffee, a widely accessible and symbolic material, this medium connects the heritage of Kelantan with contemporary art practices, making it relevant to younger generations. The research highlights the significant impact of coffee painting in raising awareness about Kelantan's culture, fostering cultural pride, and providing economic opportunities for local artists through commercialization. Furthermore, the study discusses the potential of coffee painting to be marketed as a unique cultural product, thereby contributing to the sustainable development of the local economy. By integrating traditional motifs with modern artistic techniques, coffee painting not only preserves but also revitalizes Kelantan's cultural identity, ensuring its transmission to future generations. This paper underscores the importance of innovative approaches in cultural preservation and the role of the arts in promoting sustainable cultural heritage.

Keywords: Kelantan cultural heritage, coffee painting, cultural preservation, traditional art, commercialization, sustainable development

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13888372

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1. INTRODUCTION

The cultural heritage of Kelantan, a state located in the northeastern region of Peninsular Malaysia, is a rich tapestry of traditions, beliefs, and artistic expressions that have been passed down through generations (Abdullah & Abdillah, 2021). One such unique form of cultural expression is the art of coffee painting, which has emerged as a captivating medium for preserving and showcasing Kelantan's diverse heritage (Alhamdi et al., 2023).

As a region that has long played a vital role in the maritime trade of the archipelago, Kelantan has a historical significance as the cradle of Malay culture and the cradle of Malay Heritage. The state's Malay-Islamic culture is a source of great fascination for visitors, who are struck by its ability to maintain harmony with other religious communities, demonstrating a society characterized by mutual cooperation, solidarity, and consultation, as well as religious tolerance. This rich cultural heritage is

now being celebrated and preserved through the art of coffee painting, a technique that allows artists to capture the essence of Kelantan's traditions and symbols on canvas (Best, 2006). There are a lot of Kelantan cultural heritage such Wayang Kulit in traditional performance, Wau Bulan in traditional games, Nasi Kerabu in traditional food and Rebana Ubi in traditional musical instrument.

1.1 Kelantan Traditional Performance

Kelantan is renowned for its rich traditional performances, which are deeply rooted in the region's cultural and historical heritage. These performances serve not only as entertainment but also as mediums for storytelling, cultural preservation, and community bonding.

One of the most iconic traditional performances is Wayang Kulit, a shadow puppet theatre that blends mythological storytelling with intricate puppetry and music. The Tok Dalang (puppet master) controls the puppets and narrates stories, often based on ancient epics like the Hikayat Seri Rama. This performance, accompanied by traditional musical instruments such as the rebab and gendang, captures the essence of Kelantanese folklore.

Another notable traditional performance is Mak Yong, a classical dance-drama form that combines acting, singing, and dancing. Historically performed in royal courts, Mak Yong tells stories of legendary heroes and romantic tales, accompanied by traditional music. It has been recognized as a UNESCO Intangible Cultural Heritage.

Performances like these reflect Kelantan's rich cultural tapestry, highlighting the significance of preserving these art forms in the face of modernization and global influences.

2. PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION

Kelantan's cultural heritage, like many other traditional art forms, faces the challenge of maintaining relevance and attracting the interest of younger generations in an increasingly globalized world (Suaib et al., 2020). The production of artworks that showcase heritage elements is often perceived as unacceptable at the global level, as many art practitioners may shy away from exploring these traditional motifs and techniques (Wang et al., 2023). This poses a significant threat to the preservation and transmission of Kelantan's cultural legacy (Ahmad et al., 2023).

3. BENEFITS OF THE PROJECT

The use of coffee painting as a medium for expressing Kelantan's cultural heritage offers several benefits. Firstly, it allows for the effective preservation and transmission of Kelantan's unique traditions, beliefs, and artistic expressions to future generations (Suaib et al., 2020). By creating artworks that incorporate elements of Kelantan's heritage, artists can help to maintain the relevance and appreciation of these cultural treasures in the face of globalization (Abdullah et al., 2021). Furthermore, the coffee painting medium can serve as a powerful tool for promoting Kelantan's cultural identity, both within the local community and on a global scale (Noh et al., 2015).

Moreover, the commercialization of coffee painting as a cultural art form can provide economic opportunities for local artists and artisans, contributing to the overall development of the region (Lestari et al., 2023).

4. METHOD & MATERIAL

This study employs a qualitative research approach to explore the use of coffee painting as a medium for preserving and promoting Kelantan's cultural heritage. The research is conducted in two phases: a literature review and an empirical study involving local artists and cultural practitioners.

4.1 Literature Review

The first phase involves an extensive review of existing literature on Kelantan's cultural heritage, traditional art forms, and contemporary preservation methods. Sources include academic journals, books, and online databases that provide insights into the cultural significance of traditional Kelantanese motifs and their applications in modern art practices. This review helps to establish a theoretical framework for understanding the relevance of coffee painting in cultural preservation.

4.2 Empirical Study

The second phase of the research consists of fieldwork conducted in Kelantan, where interviews and joining an event with local in coffee painting competition. A purposive sampling method is used to select participants who have significant experience and expertise in this art form. The study also includes direct observation of the artists' processes and techniques, as well as the documentation of various coffee paintings that depict Kelantanese cultural motifs.

4.3 Materials

The primary materials used in this study include:

Coffee Grounds: Sourced from locally available coffee beans, the coffee grounds serve as the primary medium for the paintings. The use of coffee as a pigment is explored for its aesthetic qualities and symbolic significance.

Canvas and Paper: Traditional canvas and high-quality paper are used as the surfaces for the coffee paintings. These materials are chosen for their ability to absorb coffee pigments effectively, preserving the integrity of the artwork over time.

Artistic Tools: Brushes, pencils, and other conventional painting tools are used to apply the coffee mixture onto the canvas. The study also experiments with different concentrations of coffee to achieve various shades and textures.

Figure 1.1 Artistic tools for coffee painting.

Figure 1.2 Canvas material for coffee painting.

Documentation Tools: High-resolution cameras and video recording devices are employed to capture the creation process and the final artworks. This documentation serves as a visual record of the study and aids in the analysis of the techniques used by the artists.

4.4 Data Analysis

The qualitative data gathered from interviews and observations are analyzed using thematic analysis. This method allows the identification of recurring themes related to the challenges and opportunities in using coffee painting as a medium for cultural preservation. The study also evaluates the effectiveness of coffee painting in conveying the cultural identity of Kelantan through its visual elements.

5. FINDINGS

This study reveals several significant insights into the use of coffee painting as a medium for preserving and promoting Kelantan's cultural heritage. The findings are organized into key themes that emerged from the data analysis, including the effectiveness of coffee painting in cultural representation, its impact on local communities, and its potential for commercialization.

5.1 Effectiveness of Coffee Painting in Cultural Representation

The study found that coffee painting effectively captures the essence of Kelantan's cultural heritage. The artists involved in the study utilized traditional motifs, such as floral patterns, mythical creatures, and geometrical designs, which are integral to Kelantan's visual identity. The use of coffee as a medium adds a unique aesthetic quality, characterized by earthy tones and a natural texture that resonate with the organic elements of Kelantanese culture. The paintings produced during the study were well-received by both local audiences and external observers, suggesting that coffee painting can serve as a powerful tool for cultural expression.

5.2 Impact on Local Communities

Interviews with local artists and cultural practitioners indicate that coffee painting has a positive impact on community engagement with cultural heritage. The competition conducted as part of the study attracted participants from various age groups, particularly younger generations, who were previously less engaged with traditional art forms. Coffee painting's modern and accessible approach makes it appealing to this demographic, fostering a renewed interest in Kelantan's cultural legacy. Moreover, the artists reported a sense of pride in contributing to the preservation of their cultural heritage through a contemporary medium.

5.3 Commercialization Potential

The findings also highlight the strong commercialization potential of coffee painting. The unique combination of traditional motifs with an unconventional medium like coffee offers a marketable product that can attract both local and international buyers. The study identified several opportunities for monetizing coffee paintings, including selling original artworks, offering workshops, and creating coffee-themed cultural merchandise. Participants expressed optimism about the economic opportunities that coffee painting could bring to the local arts community, particularly in the context of tourism. The potential for coffee paintings to be featured in galleries, exhibitions, and cultural festivals further enhances their commercial appeal.

5.4 Challenges and Recommendations

Despite the positive outcomes, the study also identified challenges in using coffee painting as a preservation tool. Some artists noted difficulties in achieving color consistency and long-term durability of the paintings, given the natural variability of coffee as a pigment. Additionally, there is a need for more structured support from cultural institutions and government bodies to promote coffee painting as a recognized art form. The study recommends further research into the technical aspects of coffee painting, such as developing more stable techniques and materials to ensure the longevity of the artworks. Additionally, establishing a formal network of coffee painting artists could help in sharing best practices and promoting this art form more widely.

6. DISCUSSION

The findings of this study underscore the significant potential of coffee painting as a novel medium for preserving and promoting Kelantan's cultural heritage. This discussion section explores the implications of these findings in the context of cultural preservation, community engagement, commercialization, and the broader challenges that arise from integrating traditional motifs with contemporary art forms.

6.1 Cultural Preservation Through Innovation

One of the key insights from this research is the effectiveness of coffee painting in capturing and conveying the cultural essence of Kelantan. By blending traditional motifs with an unconventional medium, coffee painting not only preserves cultural symbols but also revitalizes them in a form that resonates with modern audiences. This innovative approach aligns with broader trends in cultural preservation, where the fusion of traditional and contemporary elements helps to maintain the relevance of cultural heritage in a rapidly changing world. The warm, earthy tones of coffee add a distinctive aesthetic that enhances the visual representation of Kelantanese culture, making it more accessible and appealing to diverse audiences. This suggests that innovation in artistic mediums can play a crucial role in the sustainable preservation of cultural heritage.

6.2 Engaging the Younger Generation

The study's findings reveal that coffee painting has a particularly strong appeal to younger generations, who are often less engaged with traditional art forms. This engagement is critical, as it ensures the transmission of cultural knowledge and practices to future generations. The competition and community activities highlighted in the study demonstrate that coffee painting can serve as a bridge between generations, connecting young people with their cultural roots in a way that is both meaningful and contemporary. This is a significant outcome, as it addresses the challenge of cultural continuity in an era where globalization and modernization often lead to the erosion of traditional practices.

6.3 Economic Empowerment and Commercialization

The potential for commercialization identified in this study highlights an important avenue for economic empowerment within the local arts community. By turning coffee painting into a marketable product, local artists can create sustainable income streams while promoting Kelantan's cultural heritage. This aligns with broader strategies of cultural tourism, where unique and culturally significant products are leveraged to attract tourists and generate economic benefits. The commercialization of coffee painting, through the sale of artworks, workshops, and merchandise, not only enhances the visibility of Kelantanese culture but also provides a means for artists to gain recognition and financial independence. However, the study also suggests the need for careful management of

commercialization to ensure that it does not lead to the commodification of cultural symbols in a way that dilutes their meaning.

6.4 Challenges and Future Directions

While the potential benefits of coffee painting are clear, the study also points to several challenges that must be addressed to fully realize its potential. Technical issues such as color consistency and durability pose a risk to the long-term viability of coffee paintings as cultural artifacts. These challenges highlight the need for further research and development in the techniques and materials used in coffee painting. Moreover, the study calls for greater support from cultural institutions and governmental bodies to promote coffee painting as a recognized and respected art form. Establishing formal networks and collaborations among coffee painting artists could facilitate the sharing of best practices and help overcome some of these technical challenges.

Finally, the study opens up several avenues for future research. Exploring the psychological and emotional impact of coffee painting on both artists and audiences could provide deeper insights into its cultural significance. Additionally, comparative studies with other innovative art forms used in cultural preservation could further enhance our understanding of how traditional cultures can be effectively sustained in the modern world.

7. CONCLUSION

This research has explored the innovative use of coffee painting as a medium for preserving and promoting Kelantan's cultural heritage. The study has demonstrated that coffee painting, with its distinctive aesthetic qualities and deep cultural symbolism, provides a compelling means of connecting traditional Kelantanese motifs with contemporary art practices. By integrating a widely accessible and environmentally friendly material like coffee, this art form not only preserves cultural symbols but also revitalizes them, making them relevant and appealing to modern audiences, particularly the younger generation.

The engagement of local communities, especially through coffee painting competition and participatory activities, has shown that coffee painting can serve as an effective tool for cultural education and transmission. The involvement of younger generations in this artistic practice is particularly significant, as it ensures the continuity of Kelantanese cultural heritage in a rapidly changing global environment. Furthermore, the commercialization potential identified in this study suggests that coffee painting can be leveraged to create sustainable economic opportunities for local artists, contributing to both cultural preservation and economic development.

However, the study also acknowledges the challenges associated with using coffee as a painting medium, particularly in terms of achieving long-term durability and consistency. To fully realize the potential of coffee painting, further research and development are needed to refine the techniques and materials used. Additionally, greater institutional support is essential to promote coffee painting as a recognized and respected art form, both within Malaysia and internationally.

In conclusion, coffee painting represents a unique and innovative approach to cultural preservation that bridges the gap between tradition and modernity. By continuing to explore and develop this art form, there is significant potential to not only safeguard Kelantan's cultural heritage but also to share it with a wider audience, ensuring its survival and appreciation for generations to come.

Figure 2. The researchers in Coffee Painting Competition during Festival Kesenian Rakyat Kelate 2024.

Acknowledgments: I would like to express my deepest gratitude to those who have supported and contributed to the completion of this research.

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